

The accidental maximalist: Or, what’s so minimal about minimal editions?

Francesca Giannetti

October 9, 2024

Abstract

Minimal editions have become popular because they answer the problem of curating texts under a set of constraints. However, encoding and publication workflows, even for minimal editions, run the risk of becoming bloated if the editor loses sight of the project’s priorities. Over a project’s life cycle, it is normal that these priorities will shift under the pressure of this or that constraint or challenge. Several authors have noted that minimal computing stacks displace complexity away from users and onto the editor or technical partner (Dombrowski 2022; Giannetti 2019; Hughes 2016). Identifying the *necessary* technical complexity is rarely easy. I focus on the latter two of Risam and Gil’s four-question heuristic for minimal computing—“what must we prioritize?”; and “what are we willing to give up?”—in order to demonstrate the importance of reengaging with these questions as new challenges come to light (Risam and Gil 2022).

With the Personal Correspondence from the Rutgers College War Service Bureau, I initially made choices consonant with a minimal approach. The edition navigation replicated the file structure of the archival collection, organized by the name of the alumnus serving in World War I. The project schema exhibited straightforward choices regarding the encoding of people, places, and events. However, the plan to capture biographical information on each Rutgers person mentioned nearly ran aground when a single soldier mentioned fifty classmates in his letters. A desire for a more enriching reader experience led to a choice to provide subject access to the letters, which in turn brought classification and UI difficulties. In this case study, I provide substance to the hard decisions editors face amidst evolving priorities and the need to curtail some plans. Documentation of best practices in this area will serve other editors who must make pragmatic choices in the service of local knowledge production.

Short paper

What is a minimal edition? It might mean more than one thing at a time. For some, it will mean a digital edition built using a minimal computing approach, by which I mean editorial projects that focus on necessities and reduce technological and resource dependencies. For others, a minimal edition will denote an editorial approach, with the goal of creating something like a reading edition of a text, which is to say a singular text, possibly accompanied

by explanatory notes (Vanhoutte 2009). In yet a third case, a minimal edition could mean both things at the same time. This is the definition I am using to describe my approach to an online pedagogical edition: the Personal Correspondence from the Rutgers College War Service Bureau. Using a four-question heuristic proposed by Alex Gil and Roopika Risam as a launching point, I will take us on a project management tour through wants, needs, uncertainties, challenges, and some victories (Risam and Gil 2022). A minimal approach to a text can easily balloon to a maximal one when wants get in the way of outcomes. Regularly engaging with the questions—“what must we prioritize?” and “what are we willing to give up?”—has been key to pushing through various impasses. In this talk, I will describe a few of these challenges, and compare my choices to those of editors of another minimal edition. I will conclude with a few observations that I hope will assist editors facing similar challenges.

The records of the Rutgers College War Service Bureau is a collection of university records from the period of US engagement in World War I (1917-1919). The records include correspondence between the director and Rutgers men serving in the war. My involvement in the project began when digitization was complete; my role was to create opportunities to engage student researchers with the digitized materials. Given my background in text encoding, I naturally thought of a digital edition.

I will quickly dispatch with the first two questions Gil and Risam pose us. What did I need? An online edition of some sort so that students could have something to point to when they completed their work with me. What did I have? I was already aware of the Jekyll static site generator and the Ed theme for minimal editions, and it seemed natural to use it after making a handful of modifications to suit the features of correspondence. My troubles began with the second two questions, which in my experience really speak to the decision making aspects of the project plan.

As project director, I was highly motivated to learn several things myself in addition to teaching students. And I lacked the typical project management constraints that would have forced me to make binding decisions sooner. First, I have no real “client” unless it is the student encoders themselves, which switches the focus from outputs to processes. And second, this project has no funding (funders typically impose strict timelines). When I published the first letter anthologies to the web, I made a decision to replicate the structure of the archival collection itself, which is organized into files of correspondence associated with individual alumni. This structuring choice also made sense from pedagogical perspective. It is easy to assign an alumnus to one or more students so that they can spend time with a single person’s handwriting and learn more about them through archival and genealogical research. However, this choice eventually posed a challenge for online navigation, since access by alumnus name was meaningless to most readers. At an NEH institute on “Advanced Digital Editing,” I was encouraged to create wireframes for various possible interfaces. At the time, I had the institute’s chosen platform, the very much not minimal eXist-db, in mind when I drew these images, showing access by location, subject, and date. Location information struck me as important to keep, since there are many locations mentioned in the letters that are training camps throughout the US and Canada, and of course sites along or near the Western Front, and which would not be especially familiar to most readers. Consequently, part of my learning would be to extract location information from the `correspDesc` and `listPlace` elements and visualize them in an online map, preferably using open source software. I was also very

attached to the idea of subject access to individual letters, which would mean breaking up my letter anthologies by individual letters classed by subject. I had no good idea of how to accomplish this without a database, which was not an option for this project

Figure 1: Wireframes showing access by location

One of the felicitous aspects of my participation in that NEH institute was a realization that I had to relinquish some control of the edition to the student interns working with me. I did not myself have all the answers, and it was quite possible that they would have better, more actionable ideas. Madiha Maajid, an intern who was a computer science major, listened to my thoughts and hopes for subject access and my exhortation to avoid databases, and created a prototype that kept the primary access by alumnus but added secondary access by subject. This solution did not require a radical reorganization of the existing edition. She used only JavaScript, HTML, and CSS.

Following her lead, I gave up a location-based interface and instead added a Leaflet map only to those letter anthologies where it might enhance a reader's understanding of the letters. Some alumni moved about the United States, France, and elsewhere, while others stayed in the same location for their whole war; the latter men didn't need maps.

The scope of the navigation issue, and the required technologies, seemed to be narrowing, which was progress. That left the challenge of adding subject classification to the encodings and the interface. In a first pass, the students and I use the Hypothesis annotation tool to make a preliminary assignment of subjects with links to Library of Congress authorities.

Of the many potential themes to highlight, we seek the ones that are descriptive of individuals

Figure 2: ..by subject

Figure 3: ..and by date

Biographical Note

William Penn Esterbrook "Pete" Ainsworth was born in Rahway, New Jersey, in 1893. He was the eldest son of George Cornell Ainsworth and Grace Esterbrook. Ainsworth and his family were close to each other and their families so well. Ainsworth has the affectation of referring to Silvers's wife, Edith Terrill, as "friend" —perhaps a holdover from when they were dating and

Ainsworth pursued a technical Bachelor of Science course at Rutgers, where he graduated with honors in mechanical engineering in 1916. He would marry Janet Middleton Ainsworth a manager at the Combustion Engineering Corporation of New York. He published The development of an automatic combustion control for coal burning in 1935.

During the war, Ainsworth served as a captain in the 57th regiment of the Coast Artillery Corps (CAC). The role of the Coast Artillery was to provide personnel for all US-marine units in addition to coastal defense. As he mentions in a letter to his father, Ainsworth's unit was equipped with French-made weapons, specifically the 155 Grande Puissance Filloux. After training at various locations in the US and France, including the Coast Artillery School at Fort Monroe and what sounds like a very pleasant chateau in Libourne (Bordeaux) and the Meuse-Argonne Offensive.

The tone of Ainsworth's letters comes fairly close to the soldierly ideal of the time, which is to say it shows an "insouciant courage," a "studied gaiety under fire," and no hint of fear. In addition to training, Ainsworth reaches for pedestrian topics like his schedule and the food, as if to communicate that everything is normal, more than fine. The contrast with his later description of the Hindenburg Line, is striking. Ainsworth uses jocular language like "party" to describe Allied bombardments and claims to find the night-time German prisoners, who have "the face of a machine." Horror occasionally seeps through his language, as when he describes trying to get his truck out of a shell hole while with the liquidation of supplies. Like many officers, he was granted a leave to tour parts of Western Europe before returning home to the US. He includes an interesting description of a light district or if this was just another case of "khaki fever." Ainsworth was finally discharged from duty in June 1919.

Sources

John Horne, "Soldiers, Civilians and the Warfare of Attrition: Representations of Combat in France, 1914-1918," in Authority, Identity and the Social History of the Great War
 Kent, "Love and Death: War and Gender in Britain, 1914-1918," in Authority, Identity and the Social History of the Great War, ed. Frans Coetzee and Marilyn Shevin-Coetzee

Tags:

- All
- Combat
- Women
- Family
- Destruction
- Armistice
- Travel
- Routine
- Food
- Technology
- Isolation
- Germans
- Death
- Update
- Scenery
- Censorship
- Fraternity

William P. E. Ainsworth to Unknown, May 20, 1917

Figure 4: Student prototype with subject tags following biographical note

War Service Bureau
 personal correspondence from the Rutgers College War Service Bureau

Abt, David A New York born infantry soldier who served in France.	Ainsworth, William P.E. Served as Captain of the Coast Artillery Corps, born in Rahway.	Bracher, Elmer Gladstone A football player at Rutgers who was fiercely loyal to the College.	Conklin, Sherman Lindsley Bio	Costa, Joseph Louis A Chemistry student who served France during WW1.	Cubberley, Chester Curtis Bio
Grimme, August L. Bio	Groendyke, Jacob W. Bio	Jackson, Morris Bacon Bio	Johnson, John W Bio	Pelton, Graham Bio	Voorhees, John Brownlee Bio

Figure 5: Student prototype with image-based interface

Ainsworth, William P. E.

edited by Alissa Renales

Mss: <https://doi.org/doi:10.7282/T3DF6TXM>

Biographical note

William Penn Esterbrook "Pete" Ainsworth was born in Rahway, New Jersey, in 1893. He was the eldest son of George Cornell Ainsworth and Grace Esterbrook.

Figure 6: Locations of correspondents and places mentioned in correspondence associated with Captain Ainsworth

Dear Sil:

What the devil is the matter with you anyhow? You started off writing like a house a-fire and kerplunk you stopped. Is it because you [haven't] received any mail from me? You threatened to stop writing if you [didn't] hear [from me] but, if that is the reason it [isn't] my fault. I have answered every letter that I have received from you, so what more can a man do? Anyway I'm giving you this last chance. Don't think I'll write again until I hear from you. Steve White just came back from the States the other day and said that he had been down to the college and that he had seen you. He also said that we had trimmed Penn State and that we had a darn good team. You know I sure would like to see a good game of football again. Guess that I'd pretty nearly go crazy to see the old team play again. If this reaches you while Sandy is around give him my best regards. How is MIKE getting along? You all haven't been hit with the "FLU" have you? [I sure] hope that you [haven't] for I know that it is pretty bad. There has been a deuce of a lot of cases of it over here and quite a lot of it in Rahway. Do you know Elmer Hansen? He used to hang around with Herb Gehring and the Bachelor bunch. Just found out the other day that he is in the hospital with a machine gun bullet in his leg. He is the first Rahway boy that has been at the hospital and it was rather nice to see him even if I [didn't] know him very well. Gosh I pretty nearly forgot to tell you that I had seen old Delamater. Harry Janeway called up and said that he was in port so I took a trip down to see him. First time I had seen him for pretty nearly a year and a half but, he was the same old Del. [Don't] think that he has changed a bit. He was on a freight ship and thought that his next trip would be to Belfast, Ireland and that he would return to St. Nazaire so I may see him again in a couple of weeks. I sure hope so for it certainly was fine to see him again. The peeper had another sick spell lately. Think that it was the diphtheria that he had this time. He is over now and on a seven day leave in Paris. His dad

Figure 7: First pass of subject classification using Hypothesis annotation tool

as well as ones with the potential to carry over to other anthologies, but no more than 20 subjects per individual letter anthology. We use Hypothesis to highlight the segment of the letter that is about that subject. In a second step, we add the subjects to the encodings themselves via a `keywords` element in the `teiHeader` and within the letter divs. We are using something of a shortcut and adding the subjects to the `@ana` attribute inside of the opening tag of the letter div. Compare this approach to that of Kinship & Longing: Keywords for Black Louisiana.

In terms of textual evidence, the Kingship & Longing approach is preferable because the editors keep their `//seg/@ana` encoding attached to the sentences that inspired them. Their commitment to a minimal edition is manifested in their choice of only four keywords across the documents. I couldn't commit to so few subject terms, but I did cut a corner on the placement of the `@ana` attributes, which saves considerable time. On the front end, with the addition of some JavaScript, the subjects become clickable buttons that open and close the letter anthologies like an accordion, alleviating an issue of overly long web pages.

Concluding thoughts

In comparing my idealized, eXist-db inspired wireframes to where we ended, it becomes apparent that there is tension between minimalism (editorial or computational) and a flexible user experience. Note that in the long list of minimalists from the GO::DH Minimal Computing Working Group no one mentioned "minimal friction," because there is often some user friction

"Rutgers Graduate Who Saved Life of Friend in France and Won Coveted Croix de Guerre for Bravery Under Fire is Resting Comfortably in Hospital," *The Central New Jersey Home News* (New Brunswick, New Jersey), March 3, 1918, p. 13.

"Rutgers Man Falls While in Action," *The Central New Jersey Home News* (New Brunswick, New Jersey), July 11, 1918, p. 1.

Seymour, James William Davenport, ed. 1920. *History of the American Field Service in France*. Vol. 3. Boston, MA: Houghton Mifflin Company.

Subject tags

all bereavement military casualties courage

greek letter societies croix de guerre (france) draft

missionaries obituaries poetry portrait photography

religion translating and interpreting

Elizabeth J. Lindsley to Earl Reed Silvers, November 25, 1917

NEWARK N. J.
NOV 25 1917
10-PM

THIS SIDE OF CARD IS FOR ADDRESS

Earl Reed Silvers
Rutgers College
New Brunswick N. J.

```
<div type="letter" decls="#conklinl_04" ana="#religion #bereavement #casualties">
  <pb n="20"/>
  <opener>
    <dateline>
      <date when="1918-08-05">August 5, 1918.</date>
    </dateline>
    <salute>Madam,</salute>
  </opener>
  <p>It is a Catholic Chaplain attached to the <seg xml:id="fn4">8th infantry cuirassiers</seg>
    <note type="annotation" target="#fn4"><p>The prestige of the French cuirassiers: a unit of cavalry known for their elaborate uniforms, dated from the Napoleonic Wars. They were last fielded in World War I.</p>
    <ref target="https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/French_Army_in_World_War_I">addresses these lines to you. Kindly pardon me; but I thought you might who writes
  </p>
  <p>you this was with your son when the shell exploded.</p>
  <p>I liked <persName key="Conklin, Sherman L." from="1894" to="1918" role="Pr: ref="https://familysearch.org/ark:/61903/1:1:QVQR-GNWB"><orig>Herman</orig></p>
  <p>serious a nature and so
  <p>artistic a soul. We were rapidly becoming friends in spite of the fact that acquaintance was so recent. Your son, Madam was very <sic>conjenial</sic> to me.</p>
</div>
```

Figure 8: War Service Bureau subjects

ORIGINAL LANGUAGE (SPANISH) ENGLISH TRANSLATION SIDE-BY-SIDE VIEW SHOW EDITORIAL INTERVENTIONS

KEYWORDS: manumission fugitivity kinship

me present.do verbaim.te en el trib.l de Vs. demandando a dicho mi amo, p.a q.e me diese la libertad, mediante la cant.d en que fuere estimada, y ordenadole Vs. lo ejecutase asi, se hi negado ael'o, en tales Perm.- q.e habiendo me tomado con violencia y hecho me transportar a la Habit.n de D Juan Dubourg su suegro (p.a impedirme del uso del d.ro qe me asiste y natural defenza q.e en asunto de estas circunst.s, fa

Fugitivity to las Leyes me estrecho en ella con prisiones; y como quiera q.e por mis arbitrios me escapare de ella, y de las crueldad.s con qe me moles taba, hé ocurrido a esta Cuid.a a impetrar la Neta administr.n de just.a q.e Vs. distribuyes en cuia conceq.c se ha de servir Vs. mandar q.e dicho mi amo me pase la correspondte carta de libertad enfra, a cuio efecto se me tare p.r la pers.a q.e Vs. tenga p.r com.te nom brar, q.e des.e luego estoi pronta a entregare la cant.d en q.e fuese estimada, la qual me adelantara una pers.a q.e quiere sacarme del Captiverio en q.e estoi: para todo lo qe le pongo demanda en fra

Show Facsimile

```
<lb>me transportar a la <abbr>Habit.</abbr></p>
<abbr> de <persName ref="#k1081">
  <abbr>D.</abbr> <abbr> Juan Dubourg</persName>
</lb>su suegro <abbr>p.</abbr></p>
<abbr> impedirme del uso del <abbr>d.</abbr></p>
<abbr> qe me asiste
<abbr> q.</abbr></p>
<abbr> me asiste
</lb>y natural defenza <abbr>q.</abbr></p>
<abbr> en asunto de estas <abbr>circunst.</abbr></p>
<abbr>, fa
</lb>voren tanto las Leyes) me estrecho en ella con
<lb>prisiones; <seg ana="#fugitivity">y como quiera <abbr>q.</abbr></p>
<abbr>
</lb>p.</p>
<abbr> mis arbitrios me
</lb>escapare de ella, y de las <abbr>crueldad.</abbr></p>
<abbr> con <abbr>q.</abbr></p>
<abbr> me moles
</lb>taba, hé ocurrido a <placeName>esta <abbr>Cui.</abbr></p>
<abbr> a impetrar la Neta
</lb>
<abbr> administr.</abbr></p>
<abbr> de <abbr>just.</abbr></p>
<abbr>
<abbr> q.</abbr></p>
<abbr>
<abbr> Vs.</abbr></p>
<seg ana="#manumission">en cuia <abbr>conceq.</abbr></p>
<abbr>.
</lb>se ha de servir <abbr>Vs.</abbr> mandar <abbr>q.</abbr></p>
<rs ref="#k1068">dicho mi amo</rs> me pase
</lb>la <abbr>corresp.</abbr></p>
<abbr> carta de libertad <abbr>enfra</abbr>, a cuio efecto
</lb>se me tare <abbr>n.</abbr></p>
```

Figure 9: Kinship and Longing keywords

with minimal interfaces. Access points were eliminated because we could not support them within our constraints. The trick is perhaps finding an elegant balance between friction and user friendliness.

Minimalism as an approach felt at times like a straightjacket; it meant giving up on some of my personal learning objectives. But I also find the four-question heuristic to be seriously useful. Just because letter metadata can be visualized in all kinds of ways does not make that approach meaningful for every text. And as I eventually realized, the war theme and the focus on trauma required a respectful sobriety and simplicity, *not* tons of interactivity.

Finishing, at least provisionally, is important. I spent a lot of time in a deficit mindset, focusing on wants and avoiding hard choices. Being able to point to some kind of output is important for institutional validation, certainly. But it also matters for building confidence as an editor. And there is some catharsis in documenting the tradeoffs, as I have done with you today.

Works cited

- Dombrowski, Quinn. 2022. “Minimizing Computing Maximizes Labor.” *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 16 (2). <http://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/16/2/000594/000594.html>.
- Giannetti, Francesca. 2019. “‘So Near While Apart’: Correspondence Editions as Critical Library Pedagogy and Digital Humanities Methodology.” *The Journal of Academic Librarianship* 45 (5): 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2019.05.001>.
- Hughes, Joel. 2016. “Minimal Definitions - Notes.” *Minimal Computing*. <http://go-dh.github.io/mincomp/thoughts/2016/10/07/minimal-definitions-notes/>.
- Risam, Roopika, and Alex Gil. 2022. “Introduction: The Questions of Minimal Computing.” *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 16 (2). <https://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/16/2/000646/000646.html>.
- Vanhoutte, Edward. 2009. “Every Reader His Own Bibliographer – An Absurdity?” In *Text Editing, Print and the Digital World*, edited by Kathryn Sutherland and Marilyn Deegan. Digital Research in the Arts and Humanities. Farnham, England: Ashgate.